

EXAMINATION OF DRAPE-INDUCED DEFECTS USING COMPUTER X-RAY TOMOGRAPHY

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Abstract

X-ray computer tomography has been trialled as a non-destructive examination technique to elucidate defects in dry, woven carbon fibre preforms. Such defects are typically introduced as a result of mapping the cloth to complex tooling geometry; a process often referred to as drape. A conceptual tool was designed and built to create a draped preform with a significant number of defects in localised regions. Cloth deformation was confirmed using kinematic drape modelling. Preform scans highlighted the presence of significant in-plane waviness and ply wrinkles. This was then furthered through scanning of a trial composite propeller blade preform, from which a 180mm long ply wrinkle was discovered. Whilst the quality of defect imagery from X-ray computer tomography is excellent, the introduction of this process at the latter stages of part manufacture is limited by a number of factors. One such factor is the inverse relationship between sample size and final resolution of the scan data. The cost associated with the process also presents a barrier to its widespread industrial usage.

1. Introduction

Current non-destructive examination (NDE) of industrially manufactured composite parts is generally a combination of visual inspection, radiographic and ultrasound-based techniques. None of these processes yet provides the resolution required to accurately represent ply wrinkles or in-plane fibre waviness.

X-ray computer tomography (XCT) has been identified as a possible NDE technique to elucidate the internal architecture of pre-infused composite parts to identify defects introduced during manual layup and debulking. XCT has recently become

more prevalent in published literature within the composites research community due to its resolution, which can be much smaller than the size of a typical 12k tow. XCT has been used to examine the orientation of warp and weft yarns in knitted fabric composites [1], damage characterisation in self-healing composites [2] and compaction of 3D woven composites [3]. The application of XCT on examination of defects such as wrinkles and in-plane waviness is currently unreported in the published literature.

The aim of this research is to assess the capabilities and limitations of XCT within the context of drape-induced defects in woven cloths prior to resin infusion. Once the capabilities of a new NDE have been established, its appropriate usage within research and/or manufacturing can be decided. This was carried out firstly using conceptual tooling and secondly using a trial composite propeller blade; this research therefore serves as a proof-of-concept exercise for the qualitative detection of defects in draped composite parts prior to resin infusion.

2. Preliminary Testing

A preliminary test using arbitrary geometry was employed to serve as a proof-of-concept exercise for the detection of defects in pre-infused composite preforms, especially to gauge the resolution of XCT in terms of visualising individual tow trajectories.

In order to successfully identify defects, the geometry of the tool, onto which the preform was loaded, had to reliably force defects into the cloth. The part geometry in Fig. 1 shows the tool, which was designed using CATIA V5, followed by manufacturing using rapid prototyping facilities at the University of Bristol. This tool was designed to include out-of-plane curvature, which induces shear deformation of the woven cloth, therefore leading to

waviness and wrinkles. Inspiration for such a tool was taken from References [4] and [5]. The tool was 140mm x 140mm; these dimensions were deemed appropriate given the volume of the chamber of the XCT scanner and the desired resolution.

A biaxial woven cloth (HexForce G1164A 1250 TCT, carbon fibre satin weave fabric, 3k tows) was used in draping trials with a stacking sequence of $[0/90]_4$. Each ply fixed using Econotac spray, following by a hardening process at 70°C for an hour in an envelope vacuum bag. This process resulted in a stiff, portable preform. The final preform was not deformed through manual handling. Transportation and setup of the preform in the scanner did not, therefore, further disrupt tow trajectories.

3. Virtual draping trials

The sequence by which woven cloths are conformed over complex geometry directly affects the quality of the final drape [6]. Before any draping was carried out, a number of Virtual Fabric Placement (VFP) simulations were performed with the aim of finding a draping sequence that would lead to significant defects. This software, developed at the University of Bristol, uses drape kinematics to calculate shear angles of woven cloths [7]. Tool geometry is imported from a CATIA surface model via a stereo lithography (stl) file. The user then directs the application of a cloth to the surface, which deforms accordingly. The result of which shows a contour plot of nodal shear deformation (ie. angle between warp and weft yarns) and therefore indicates areas of in-plane misalignment.

A number of possible draping sequences were explored. These sequences, shown in Fig. 2, were designed to give a range of possible drape morphologies, whilst being possible from the point of view of the laminator. Fig. 3 shows the output from VFP for drape sequence 3, showing areas of significant shearing. In order to determine the severity of shear deformation and quantitatively compare VFP trials, a Matlab programme was written to read the text-based output and return a weighted score.

The Matlab script reads in the output file from VFP, which contains the shear deformation of each node (as well as other vector data). The deformation data

is then passed through a weighted mean calculation, which outputs a Drape Factor Score (DFS) for each VFP output file. Lower scores indicating a drape sequence leading to less shear deformation of the cloth; consequently a “better” drape. The greater the DFS the more severe the cloth shearing is, and therefore the likelihood of waviness and wrinkles increases.

The weighted mean used to calculate DFS is shown in Equation 1, in which n is the number of nodes, y is the deformation at each node from VFP and \hat{y} is the deformation about each rounded to its nearest integer. Equation 1 provides a convenient method of summarising the quantitative data from VFP outputs, although is not a standard statistical equation. The factor of ten used in the calculation provides a clear penalty for higher severities of cloth shear angles.

$$DFS = \frac{\sum (\hat{y} \cdot 10 \times y)}{n} \quad (1)$$

Table 1 shows the results of the VFP drape trials, showing that drape 4 had the highest DFS of 2.47. Whilst sequence 4 had the most severe deformation, it was decided that drape sequence 3 would give distinct areas of “good drape” and “bad drape,” rather than simply a large amount of “bad drape.” The high DFS of sequence 3 shows the shear deformation remains relatively high. A $[0/90]_4$ layup was therefore manufactured following drape sequence 3 in preparation for scanning.

4. XCT Scanning

The detailed physics behind this method of scanning are not discussed in this paper. Instead, the basics of the process are discussed, followed by the details of the scans conducted on composite preform specimens.

4.1 XCT: Basics

A basic schematic for an XCT scanner is shown in Fig. 4. The tungsten target acts as the source of X-rays, which are then transmitted through the specimen, followed by their detection by an amorphous silicon detector. The X-rays have a modulated intensity, which depends on the overall linear attenuation characteristics of the specimen. The varying intensity with respect to distance is referred to as a profile [8]. It is this profile, which is

essentially a plot of intensity against material density that is then reconstructed and interpreted by software for display and user interrogation.

Visualisation of results also requires high-performance computational capabilities, as well as bespoke software. Interrogation of the data can be done in two ways; either using 3D volume rendering or through 2D slice viewing, which can be done in all three x , y and z directions. Both techniques are useful when analyzing XCT data and should be used together for a complete picture of the defects present.

4.2 XCT Method

The four-ply preform was scanned at the National Composites Centre (NCC), Bristol, UK. The apparatus is shown as a schematic in Fig. 4, in which the sample is loaded onto a stage, which is housed within the XCT scanning chamber. The stage is able to move in the x direction, depending on the size of the sample being scanned. During the scanning process, the stage rotates around the z -axis, allowing a full 360° scan of the sample.

A total of 1000 scans around the 360° rotation of the part were taken. A tungsten target was used to generate X-rays. An amorphous silicon detector was used, with dimensions 2000×2000 16 bit pixels. The scanning voltage used at the NCC was 100kV ($120\mu\text{A}$). A 250ms exposure time was used.

The scans were reconstructed using Nikon CTPro software on high-performance desktop computers. Hardware used typically consisted of 12 core Intel Xeon processors with either 32GB or 96GB of RAM and 2GB of high performance video RAM, depending on the specific machine. High-performance hardware is required to process and render the data. Each scan took roughly 15 minutes to complete. The reconstruction process converts the raw data from the XCT scanner to a useable format, which required between 15 and 30 minutes to complete. Interrogation of reconstructed data was carried out on similarly high-performance computers using VGMax Studio 2.1.

5. Results: XCT Scanning

XCT scanning of the trial geometry revealed a number of defects, including in-plane waviness of tows, wrinkling of plies, ply bridging and ply

separation. Waviness, ply wrinkles and ply bridging are discussed in turn.

5.1 In-plane waviness

In-plane fibre waviness is a significant problem in composite materials due to the reduction in compressive strength this defect can cause [9]. Due to the reduction in compressive strength caused by waviness, this defect is often the cause of component rejection on the shop floor.

Waviness was observed at a number of locations on the part, all of which corresponded to the deformation suggested by VFP. 3D volume rendering, as well as interrogation of the plies in a single Cartesian direction, showed in-plane waviness of tows in all four plies, as shown in Fig. 5. This Figure highlights the ability for XCT scanning to not only fully reveal the waviness on the surface plies (tiles a and b), but also plies within the stacking sequence (tiles c and d). This is important because visual inspection may be adequate to examine the surface plies of a shop-floor component for in-plane waviness, however it cannot examine plies within the stack.

The resolution of the technique is sufficient to show the path of the tows. Fig. 5a clearly shows tows that have become wavy due to compressive forces associated with draping the cloth to the tool.

5.2 Ply Wrinkles

Out-of-plane ply wrinkles are also of concern to manufacturers of composite components due to the knock-downs in mechanical performance associated with this defect. Reductions in compressive strength of up to 40% have been reported in the literature [10] due to the presence of this defect.

A ply wrinkle has been shown in Fig. 6, in which the plies within the wrinkle have been highlighted with coloured lines. From this Figure, it is evident that the first ply has wrinkled, causing the second ply also to wrinkle into an *S*-shape. Plies 3 and 4 have been forced to accommodate this wrinkle by displacing in the through-thickness direction. Visualisation of this wrinkle has been made possible through interrogation of the 2D sections of the XCT scan. From Fig. 6 it is possible to imagine the formation of a resin rich zone in the delta of the wrinkle after resin infusion.

5.3 Ply bridging

Plies that bridge tooling radii are of concern due to the propensity of this defect to cause further defects, such as ply wrinkles, during consolidation [11], [12] and resin-rich regions in the infused composite.

Fig. 7 shows a 3D volume render as well as 2D slice, highlighting the formation of bridged plies. The resolution of XCT shows that the ply bridging is located on the same side of the two features of the tool, and that the bridging becomes more severe through the ply stack. The identification of ply bridging relies on both 3D and 2D visualisation techniques.

5.4 Preliminary Study: Conclusions

Fig. 5, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show examples of the capabilities of defect visualisation with XCT scanning. The resolution is sufficient to distinguish individual tows, as well as their trajectory and pick out deformed ply paths in wrinkles. Combining the use of both 2D and 3D interrogation techniques gives the full picture of the defects in the part. As shown in Fig. 3, this is of course a worst-case scenario, in which the tool has been designed to produce defective preforms.

6. XCT scanning of industrial preforms

The preliminary study showed the capabilities of XCT for defect elucidation using proof-of-concept tool geometry. The study was then furthered by scanning trial preforms with complex geometry to assess its capabilities in the context of industrially relevant components. A propeller blade spar former was used with a variable cross-section, going from semi-circular at the “root” followed by a transition to a flat aerofoil. The former was 2m long. In order to maximise the probability of a defect being found within the scanned preform, it was laid up by operators with minimal shop floor experience.

Plies of cloth were laid up into the former individually according to a given stacking sequence. Both unidirectional cloth at a 0° fibre direction (ie. tows are oriented from root to tip) and biaxial satin cloth at ±45° directions were used. The unidirectional cloth used was treated with a thermoplastic binder by the manufacturer, and did not require the Econotac treatment. Instead the use of a heat gun and manual forming actions resulted in

a stiff preform that was easy to handle. Vacuum debulking was carried out at 125°C for 2 hours in a purpose-made silicone debulking bag.

The length of the preform exceeded the scan chamber of the XCT equipment at the NCC. Region of interest (ROI) scanning is not an effective technique for XCT scanning. Sections of the sample will rotate in and out of the attenuation field, which creates artefacts within the reconstructed image.

The laid up blade spar was therefore cut into 120mm long sections using an ultrasonic knife. The use of an ultrasonic knife resulted in clean edges of the preform with minimal fraying of the carbon tows and did not require the use of an aqueous lubricant, therefore the original path of tows was maintained during the cutting process. Five sections were taken from the root of the preform out to the flat aerofoil section.

The first, fourth and fifth sections were defect-free. Sections two and three showed evidence of a ply wrinkle formed at the leading edge of the aerofoil of the preform. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 highlight this ply wrinkle. These figures show a capability of the VGMax software to colour-code XCT data according to material density.

From these figures it is possible to identify the different plies used in the construction of the spar; biaxial satin cloth tends to show up green, whilst the unidirectional cloth shows up as purple. The density-dependent colour coding of XCT data is also a useful technique for examining the trajectory of tracer fibres within woven cloth, which are frequently denser than the surrounding carbon-based tows.

Fig. 8 shows the wrinkle begins 76mm along the second section of the preform as the first two plies at the tool surface begin to separate. This wrinkle becomes worse along the length of the section; at 107mm the wrinkle is at its most significant. Fig. 9 shows the “transition” between the root and aerofoil cross sections of the blade, where the wrinkle begins to flatten. At 125mm into the third section of the preform all plies are visibly in contact with no signs of the defect. XCT has, in this case, shown the length of the wrinkle to be 180mm long.

Acquiring images of in-plane waviness in the middle of a layup, such as Fig. 5d, requires the component to

be flat. Estimations of fibre waviness in the circular root section were consequently not possible. This is a key limitation of XCT; the interrogation surface must be flat.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

A proof-of-concept study has been carried out to assess the capabilities of XCT to elucidate drape-induced defects in carbon fibre woven cloth using conceptual tooling geometry. XCT was able to show defects such as in-plane fibre waviness (Fig. 5), ply wrinkles (Fig. 6) as well as ply bridging (Fig. 7) and ply separation. The tool used was a “worst case scenario,” in which VFP trials showed that a significant amount of shearing was required to map the cloth to the surface of the tool.

An industrially relevant trial propeller blade spar preform was then passed through the same process. XCT was able to highlight the presence of a 180mm long ply wrinkle in the transition from circular root to flat aerofoil section. 2D slices showed how this ply wrinkle resulted in excess length of two plies to be accounted for by ply separation (Fig. 8 and Fig. 9). Defects of this magnitude are likely to result in part rejection.

The use of software, such as VGMax Studio, allows for the data to be manipulated in such a way that exposes a number of defects, which is a result of the fantastic resolution offered by the x-ray interrogation medium.

From these two trials, it is clear XCT is a powerful technique to examine pre-infused parts for defects. The detail provided by the resolution of the X-rays surpasses that of other NDE techniques and would be an invaluable addition to the NDE suite present in many composite manufacturing lines.

There are, however, a number of limitations to the widespread use of this technique in production parts. Firstly, the inverse relationship between the size of the sample and the final resolution of the data prevents large parts from being scanned whole. XCT machines designed for materials testing restrict the size of the sample to the volume of the scanning chamber. Whilst sectioning the parts, as done in this work, sufficiently reduces the physical size of the specimen for adequate resolution, this process negates XCT’s credentials for being a non-destructive process.

Secondly, examination of in-plane waviness in plies within the ply stack relies on a flat surface. Complex geometries, such as those in propeller blades and wind turbine blades, may not have flat surfaces and so XCT may be of limited use to examine in-plane waviness.

XCT should continue to be considered as an emerging technology in the field of composites manufacturing. Whilst it may not be suitable to scan and examine every part coming off the production line, it has the potential to be a tool to aid the development and design of resin infused parts, particularly from a “design for manufacture” point of view. Its application in central research facilities, such as the NCC, with financially supporting members is currently the best approach for the implementation of XCT. Members can therefore access the XCT scanning facilities to develop products and layup guidelines, before using traditional ultrasonic-based methods for NDE and certification.

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Fig. 1: Geometry of tooling manufactured to form defects in woven carbon cloth during the process of drape.

Fig. 2: Drape sequences 1 through 4. The start point of each drape is shown with a red cross. Each red line corresponds to the direction of fixing the cloth to the surface of the tool geometry in the order specified. Higher Drape Factor Score numbers indicate greater shear deformation about the nodes, and suggest the formation of defects such as waviness and wrinkles.

Fig. 3: VFP drape simulation of drape sequence 3, as well as the colour-coded reference. Tool surface (yellow) is based on Fig. 1. The deformation about each node is the angle between warp and weft tows.

Fig. 4: Schematic of XCT scanning facilities at the National Composites Centre, Bristol. Figure adapted from Ref [2].

Fig. 5: In-plane fibre waviness discovered in XCT scans. Tiles “a” and “b” show waviness of the volume rendered scans in plies 4 and 1, respectively. Tile “c” shows the waviness in the second ply, which is then shown in the zoom tile, “d.” Regions of waviness are highlighted with red arrows. Glass fibre tracer tow have been false coloured in yellow.

Fig. 6: Formation of a ply wrinkle in a 4 ply preform. (a) shows the 2D scan of the wrinkle. Plies have been highlighted in (b) with solid lines.

Fig. 7: Ply bridging in conceptual preform. (a) shows a 2D slice of the 3D render, location shown by the green line in (b). The positions of the bridged plies is highlighted with red arrows.

Fig. 8: False colour images of the second 120mm section from a trial propeller blade spar preform XCT scan at three positions along the section. Region positions are shown for each tile. Position of wrinkle highlighted with arrows.

Fig. 9: False colour images of the third 120mm section from a trial propeller blade spar preform XCT scan. The arrows on these scans are coincident with the arrows highlighting the wrinkle in **Fig. 8**.

Table 1: Drape Factor Scores for drape sequences 1 through 4. A higher DFS suggests a drape sequence leading to greater cloth deformation.

Drape Sequence (Fig. 2)	1	2	3	4
Drape Factor Score	0.73	0.87	1.44	2.47

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